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Chemical Examination of Flowers of *Asparagus gonocladus* Baker

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ASPARAGUS gonocladus, Baker¹ (N.O. Liliaceae) known as Shakakul in Hindi is used in the indigenous system of medicine for various ailments. Previous studies have shown the presence of asparagine¹ in other species.

The fresh flowers were repeatedly extracted in the cold with successive quantities of methanolic hydrochloric acid (1%). The red coloured combined extract so obtained responded to colour tests for the presence of anthocyanins². Paper chromatographic examination revealed the presence of only one anthocyanin which was crystallised from a mixture of acetone and ether as red crystals, C₂₉H₃₅O₁₇Cl, m.p. 165°(d), λ_{max}530 nm, ν_{max}^{Nujol} 3380, 1638, 1555, 1498, 1460, 1432, 1346, 1180, 1042, 932, 910, 886, 820, ..., etc. cm⁻¹. The compound on hydrolysis with 7 per cent. sulphuric acid yielded Malvidine chloride, C₁₇H₁₅O₇Cl, m.p. above 300°, λ_{max}542 nm, ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1640, 1550, 1500, 1464, 1430, 1350, 1170, 1040, ..., etc. cm⁻¹, and glucose (identified by co-chromatography with the authentic sample and osazone formation). The quantitative estimation of sugar moiety by colorimetric method³ showed the presence of glucose and Malvidine chloride in the molar ratio of 2 : 1. The anthocyanin was identified to be Malvin chloride by mixed m.p. with the authentic sample.

The flowers were washed with ethanol and then exhaustively extracted with 80 per cent. ethanol. The ethanolic extract responded to colour test with ninhydrin for the presence of amino acids. Paper chromatographic examination revealed the presence of an amino acid. Its identity was confirmed by co-chromatography with the authentic sample of asparagine.

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Carboxylation of Pyrazolones and Application of the Products

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IN continuation of our reports on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁴, in which it has been noted that 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast fungus *Pyricularia Oryzae*, we have tried to synthesise some water soluble carboxy derivatives of 2-pyrazolin-5-ones herein, for their application as systemic fungicides. A compound, to behave as a systemic fungicide must have high water solubility in order to be absorbed by the rice plant from the soil. It has been observed that carboxylation of 2-pyrazolin-5-one nucleus renders it more water soluble.

It had been reported⁵ that carboxylation of resorcinol can be effected by heating in water with potassium bicarbonate at 100°. As 2-pyrazolin-5-one nucleus has marked similarity with phenolic compounds, the same method is applied here to carboxylate 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and 3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one.

Six carboxy acids were prepared and screened for antifungal activity against the fungus *P. Oryzae* by the standard method⁶. The details of the observations on these compounds are given in Table 1. It has been observed that all these compounds except compound No. 4, exhibited more fungicidal activity than the corresponding compounds without the carboxy groups. Fungicidal activity of all these later compounds have been reported earlier^{1,8}.

Amongst these, compounds 2 and 5 are found to be the most effective potential systemic fungicides,

and are now under investigation at C. R. R. I., Cuttack, by pot application.

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	M.P. (°C)	% Yield	Concn. in parts per million	% of inhibition of spore germination
1.	Ph	H	COOH	189	70	1000	95
2.	Ph	NO	COOH	162	95	250	100
3.	Ph	Br	COOH	132	65	1000	80
4.	H	H	COOH	205	70	1000	75
5.	H	NO	COOH	240	90	500	100
6.	H	Br	COOH	195	65	1000	85

Compounds No. 1 and 4 are prepared by the carboxylation method described⁵ for resorcinol and also by the method reported elsewhere⁷. The products from both the methods are found to be identical. Compounds No. 2, 5 and 3, 6 are prepared by the methods of nitrosation and bromination respectively as reported earlier^{1,2} from this laboratory. The elemental analysis of all the compounds are quite satisfactory.

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Studies on Tripropyltin Dithiocarbamates

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IN continuation to our studies on diorgano dithiocarbamates of organometal moieties, we report the preparation, characterisation, and structure of some new tripropyltin dithiocarbamates of the general formula (Pr₃Sn₂dtc) (where dtc = morpholine-, piperidine-, dibutyl-, N-methylaniline-, diethyl-, N-methylaniline-dithiocarbamates).

Experimental

Bis(tri-propyltin) oxide was obtained from Alfa Inorganics (U.S.A.). Amines and solvents were purified by conventional methods. Physico-chemical measurements were made as reported earlier¹.

A representative method for the preparation of tripropyltin morpholine dithiocarbamate is given below:—

To a mixture of bis(tri-propyltin) oxide (10 mmole) and carbon disulphide (10 ml) in chloroform (20 ml), morpholine (20 ml) in the same solvent (10 ml) was added dropwise at ~ -20°. After 2 hrs. stirring, the excess of chloroform was distilled off at reduced pressure and the residual liquid was extracted with ether which on distillation yielded yellow oily tripropyltin morpholine dithiocarbamate. Yield 70%.

Results and Discussion

Tripropyltin dithiocarbamates have been prepared by the following reaction:—

The reactions were carried out in an organic solvent such as chloroform, benzene or methanol. The analytical data presented in the Table 1 agree well with the proposed stoichiometry. The compounds are high boiling oily liquids, soluble in common organic solvents such as benzene, methanol, acetone and diethylether. Molecular weight determination by cryoscopic method and electrical conductance studies in absolute methanol indicate that the compounds are monomers and non-electrolytes in solution. They are stable at room temperature.

The infrared spectra have been examined in KBr, nujol and solution and it has been observed that there is neither matrix interaction nor changes in solution. An examination of C-N stretchings in infrared spectra of the compounds at $1465 \pm 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, shows that the absorption is sensitive to the